

METHICILLIN RESISTANCE STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS (MRSA): CHARACTERISTICS AND METHODS OF PREVENTING THE EMERGENCE AND SPREAD OF STRAINS

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Introduction. *Staphylococcus aureus* is bacterium of humans that is becoming more clinically important due to its fast development resistance to antibiotics. Some of *S. aureus* varieties are methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* that called (MRSA). Usually healthcare-associated MRSA it occurs in hospitals, nursing home, dialysis centers. MRSA affects people with weakened immune systems, surgical wounds, or invasive devices (like catheters) and etc. The severity of infections associated with this pathogen, severe complications and death make the significance of MRSA one of the important objects of research and requires improvements since the resistance of the microorganism only increases every year.

Purpose of the study. To study of characteristics and methods of preventing the emergence and spread of strains of methicillin resistance *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA).

Materials and methods. This research analyzes based on references including Science Direct, Web of Science, Scopus, Pub Med, EBSCO published until February 2025 using several keywords such as *methicillin resistance Staphylococcus aureus, diseases, antibiotic resistance* and their combinations.

Results of the research. *Staphylococcus aureus* is the clinically significant species of opportunistic pathogen, colonizing up to 50% of the human population as part of the typical commensal flora of humans. *S. aureus* infections can range from simple, superficial skin infections to harmful. Hospital infections caused by this pathogen, particularly is currently recognized as the most common cause of infective endocarditis and many different diseases. Staphylococcal toxins which like leukocidin (PVL), alpha-toxin, food poisoning and toxic shock is connected with severe infections. Antibiotic resistance of pathogens increases with increased usage, primarily due to novel selection, gene and strain epidemics. Antimicrobial resistance is a growing global concern where it is becoming a significant public health issue due to the increasing use of broad-spectrum antibiotics. Methicillin was used in the clinic in 1959 and was effective in managing penicillin-resistant *S. aureus* infections. Only in 1961 was reported the isolation of an MRSA strain. This resistance was triggered by a gene (*mecA*). For now MRSA is divided into two categories, community-acquired MRSA (CAMRSA) and hospital-acquired MRSA (HA-MRSA), according to its initial source.

Conclusions. Widespread use of antibiotics has led to the growth of bacterial resistance, starting with the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains such as MRSA, and clinically important problem and attracted extensive attention of researchers. MRSA has become an obstacle in clinical therapy due to its characteristics, rapid infection, and high mortality. In order to prevent the emergence and control of MRSA, it is necessary to rationally use antibiotics, develop guidelines, standards for the appropriate use of antibiotics.